

AN INTER-INDUSTRY ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH COMMUNICATION SKILLS VALUED BY EMPLOYERS IN PAKISTAN: A SURVEY OF HR MANAGERS AND RECRUITERS

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Abstract

English being lingua franca is a door-way to career growth in today's globalized world. English is essential for new graduates to succeed in their careers. English is the official language and the main means of communication and correspondence in professional settings in Pakistan's cutthroat job market. To match education with industrial demands, it is critical to comprehend what recruiters expect. The basic aim of the research is to explore recruiters' preference for specific English skills for job allotment. It is a quantitative, repeated measures design. The total of 19 companies' data was collected from Karachi. A convenient sampling technique was utilized. Hiring professionals from diverse industries participated in the research such as Information Technology, Manufacturing Industry, Educational Institutes and Health Sectors. Data was analysed using IBM SPSS version 21. A paired sample T- test was performed to compare means of speaking and writing skills. The mean difference of two skills is 3.7894 with standard deviation of 2.25. The t statistics are 7.340 with df 18. The data indicates that recruiters place a high value on overall English language proficiency. The candidate with the highest degree of confidence is hired. It has been discovered that pronunciation, general confidence, and enunciation all affect employment prospects. The paired sample t test also makes it evident that the hiring staff values speaking abilities above writing abilities.

INTRODUCTION

Effective communication is crucial for job advancement because it allows people to develop relationships, present ideas clearly, and overcome obstacles at work (Kapur, 2025). Since they can inspire and motivate others through persuasive and clear communication, effective communicators are frequently seen as leaders (Chikwe, 2024; Lashari & Umrani, 2023). Through excellent communication, one can establish solid professional relationships that

can lead to career advancement and new opportunities. Effective communicators are frequently more noticeable to colleagues and superiors, which can result in recognition and job development (Darmawan, 2024; Lashari, Umrani & Buriro, 2021). Since they show that a person can contribute to the success of the company, effective communication skills can have a big impact on performance reviews (Gerald, 2024). Both corporate

performance and personal professional progress depend on effective communication (Mustafa, 2024). It promotes career advancement and organizational success by creating a favourable work atmosphere, increasing productivity, strengthening bonds with coworkers, and facilitating problem-solving (Obodozie, 2025; Abbasi et al., 2020; Simming, Asad & Lashari, 2015; Salman et al., 2023). Effective communication reduces mistakes and maximizes performance by ensuring that everyone is aware of their roles and responsibilities (Darmawan, 2024). Good communication creates a constructive and encouraging atmosphere where team members can collaborate well, which improves creativity and problem-solving (Badriyah, 2024; Lashari et al., 2023). Relationships are strengthened and general morale is raised when open and honest communication is maintained with stakeholders, clients, and staff (Okunade, 2025). Operations run more smoothly and there are fewer disputes when there is clear communication to avoid misunderstandings and arguments (Lashari et al., 2028; Uwamusi, 2025). Effective information sharing enables teams to make quicker, better-informed decisions, which benefits the success of the organization (Fayaz et al., 2023). Effective communication is the cornerstone of human connection and has an impact on everything from interpersonal relationships to organizational success (Bukhari, 2025; Lashari & Umrani, 2021; Lashari et al., 2023)

Role of English in Job Market:

There are several long-term advantages to investing in English language instruction in Pakistan, especially with regard to employability and professional progression (Abbas, 2025). Due to its role as a global lingua franca, competency in English is essential for success in a variety of professional disciplines (Murali, 2025). In today's globalized world, this ability is a great advantage since it not only improves employment opportunities but also makes it easier to integrate into different cultures (Arsalani, 2025; Lashari et al., 2023). Its involvement in education, work, and economic prospects highlights the significance of English in Pakistan and reflects its deeply ingrained place in the nation's sociopolitical framework (Mehboob, 2025). Proficiency in English is crucial for career advancement in Pakistan since it's frequently

needed for efficient communication in meetings and presentations (Abro, 2025; Lashari et al., 2023). Because English is a vital ability in many areas, mastering it is associated with better work opportunities and higher incomes (Sadaf, 2025). Institutions of higher learning are urged to provide settings that improve students' English-speaking skills, which are essential for professional success (Abbasi et al., 2019; Lashari et al., 2018; Zeg, 2025). The ability to speak and understand English is one of the top five talents required for both domestic and foreign work (Khoiruman, 2025). People who are fluent in English have an advantage in the employment market because of the language's historical and sociocultural dominance in Pakistan (Noor, 2025; Lashari & Umrani, 2023). Globally, being able to communicate in English is highly valued and regarded as a means of accessing better professional prospects (Ahamed, 2025). English has a substantial economic value in Pakistan since it is linked to distinct incomes and advantages for people from different sociopolitical backgrounds (Sabir, 2025).

English Communication: The Graduates Edge.

Pakistan's youth offer a potential demographic dividend in addition to being strategically significant to the country's development (Sharif, 2025). Pakistan's economy is still in its infancy (Rashid, 2025; Hussain, 2025). A country's progress and growth depend on its educational system (Jarilkapovich, 2025). The importance of education for social and economic growth has been demonstrated by earlier studies (Li, 2025; Ganda, 2025; Halili, 2025). After graduating, every young person seeks work in both public and private institutions (Lashari et al., 2018). Job seekers are drawn to positions with high standards of labor and quality (Wang, 2025; Ahmed, Lashari & Golo, 2023). Pakistan ought to increase jobs and improve working conditions.

In an increasingly interconnected global economy, English communication skills have emerged as a cornerstone for professional success and employability across diverse industries (Jarilkapovich, 2025). Proficiency in English communication is essential for recent graduates' employability since it has a big impact on their capacity to get employment and grow in their professions (Roshid & K., 2025). Employers in a variety of industries stress the value of

fluency in English and associate it with increased workplace efficiency and production (Seti, 2025). English communication skills are regularly ranked as essential by employers when making hiring decisions, and many claim that graduates' high jobless rates are a result of their poor communication skills (Lashari & Umrani, 2023; Sekar, 2025). Because good communication is frequently linked to leadership and collaborative skills, fluency in English not only helps one land a job but also offers avenues for career advancement (Al-Tamimi, 2025). In a labor market that has gone global, since English is the main language of business, graduates who want to compete globally must be proficient in it (Lashari et al., 2018, Rashid, 2025). Standardized English proficiency exams are promoted by employers as an objective way to evaluate applicants' communication abilities during the hiring process (Campion, 2025). Workplace simulators are being used more and more in recruitment processes to assess candidates' confidence and real-time communication skills (Amrutha, 2024). Strong English communication improves the ability to communicate ideas clearly, listen intently, and solve problems—all of which are qualities that employers seek in graduates (Abro, 2025; Roshid, 2025). Although there is a lot of emphasis on English communication skills, others contend that this emphasis could obscure other vital abilities like technical know-how or creativity, which are also important for employability in a variety of areas. A well-rounded graduate profile requires striking a balance between these competencies.

The transition of recent university graduates from academia to the workforce frequently depends not only on their technical proficiency but also on their capacity for clear communication of ideas, productive teamwork, and professional English representation (Bukhari, 2024; Demafeliz, 2025). This is especially true in nations like Pakistan, where English has a status of official language and being able to communicate in English is essential for business, trade, and international interaction, making it a crucial factor in determining one's career path (Sadaf S. G., 2025). Through the methodical collection and analysis of recruiters' perspectives, this study seeks to provide specific data on which of these broad skill sets is considered more important in the hiring process. The results will offer insights for educational

institutions to enhance their curricula, career counsellors to provide targeted advice, and graduates to strategically invest in the communication abilities appreciated by employers in Pakistan. The importance of speaking English is widely known, but little research has been done on the specifics of what employers consider to be "effective" communication. Conventional wisdom often assumes that oral (speaking) and written communication are equally important and thus broadly classify them. It is occasionally unclear, though, if recruiters give specific writing skills a higher premium than overall communicative competency. The perceived "employability gap" could be exacerbated by this uncertainty since it causes a mismatch between the skills graduates learn in universities and value most in their development and the actual demands of the workplace.

Research Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference in the perceived importance ratings of speaking skill and writing skill among recruiters.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant difference in the perceived importance ratings of speaking skill and writing skill among recruiters.

Problem Statement:

Effective English communication is of paramount importance to climb up career ladder (Pawar, 2024). English is indispensable for fresh graduates to excel in their career (Hastuti, 2025). Although English writing and speaking both are considered equally important yet there is a lack of empirical proves regarding the differential emphasis paid by employers (Victor, 2025). In the competitive Pakistani job market English serves as an official language and primary language of communication and correspondence in professional setting. It is important to understand recruiters' expectations so that education can be aligned with industry needs (Awashreh, 2025). The ambiguity can lead to miss job opportunities despite having educational degrees. It can perpetuate the gap between recruiters' expectations and graduates' communication abilities. Therefore, the research seeks to bridge the gap by the identification of the skills required by recruiters so that the demanded skill

can be given more weightage in education sector. The findings will help optimizing career guidance, curriculum design to equip students with the industry-required skills.

Literature Review:
Connected Theories

Human Capital Theory: Human Capital Theory is the work of Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz. It sees education and training as investments that raise a person's earning potential and productivity. In 1961, Schultz and Becker are recognized for having developed and popularized the theory, while Jacob Mincer also made a substantial contribution. Schultz, who is frequently credited with coining the current human capital theory, highlighted the importance of education and training as investments that raise a person's earning potential and productivity (Schultz, 1961). He made the case that these expenditures might be seen as "embodied education," which has the potential to provide greater earnings in the future. These economists essentially saw education as an investment that raises a person's stock of human capital, which in turn raises productivity and, eventually, earnings, rather than just a consumption item. The study specifically aligns with human capital

theory. Graduates invest their amount and time to earn these skills in universities. This research talks about employer valuation to the skills by finding out which skills are most demanded by recruiters to meet the industry requirement.

According to the human capital hypothesis, training and education are investments that raise a person's earning potential and productivity, which promotes economic progress and the welfare of society. It emphasizes how important education is to creating a competent labour force and encouraging creativity, making it a vital component of both personal and societal advancement (Becker, 1992). Over the course of their careers, those with greater education and skill levels typically make more money. Education increases one's employability and opens up more favourable employment prospects. People from underprivileged backgrounds can raise their socioeconomic standing with education. Education promotes communication, problem-solving, and critical thinking abilities, all of which support general personal development. Social cohesion, civic participation, and informed citizenship are all enhanced by education. Economic growth, productivity, and creativity are all fuelled by a workforce with a high level of education.

Fig 1: Human Capital Theory of Becker 1992

Competency Theory: Renowned psychologist David McClelland was well-known for his work on competency modelling and motivation. He studied human motivation and success in great detail while he was a professor at Harvard University. The McClelland Competency Model, sometimes referred to as the Competency Model, was created as a result of McClelland's proficiency in competency modelling

(McClelland, 1998).The desire to determine and quantify the essential talents needed for success in a variety of roles and professions motivated the creation of the Competency Model. McClelland understood that job performance and success could not be predicted just by traditional measures of intelligence and abilities. According to him, effective performance in the workplace requires competences, which are a

collection of knowledge, skills, talents, and personal traits. The requirement for a thorough framework to comprehend and evaluate individual competencies led McClelland to create the Iceberg Model of Competencies. According to McClelland's Iceberg Model of Competencies, competencies are made up of both obvious and obscure elements. The hidden component symbolizes the underlying motivations, characteristics, and values that underlie the visible component, which stands for the observable abilities and actions that people exhibit throughout performance. The paradigm states that the hidden component is the cornerstone of competences and is essential to a person's success and efficacy in a certain field. A framework that identifies and describes the essential competencies needed for success in particular jobs or occupations is the Competency Model, which was created by McClelland. It highlights the value of both technical proficiency and character traits like drive, self-assurance, and flexibility. To enhance job performance and organizational success, the model offers a systematic method for evaluating and cultivating key competencies in people. In the fields of human resource management and organizational behaviour, the competency model is crucial (Nayebpour, 2024). It offers a thorough framework for comprehending and evaluating the skills required to succeed in a variety of occupations. By recognizing and cultivating these competencies, organizations may enhance worker performance, job satisfaction, and overall organizational effectiveness (Putra, 2024). The Competency Model emphasizes the significance of individual traits and behaviours in effective leadership, which has implications for leadership development as well.

According to competency theory, it's critical to recognize and evaluate certain, observable actions that signify competence. Competencies are relevant and actionable because they are frequently defined in connection to particular tasks, responsibilities, or circumstances. According to the Four Stages of Competence Model, competency development is

frequently viewed as a process in which people move from unconscious incompetence to unconscious competence (Sposato, 2025). Competencies can be divided into two categories: functional competencies, which are exclusive to a given job role, and core competencies, which are general and organizational (Calhau, 2024). This entails developing a framework that lists the precise skills needed to succeed in a given position or company. The psychological need to grow and prove one's abilities is the main focus of this idea, along with ways to encourage this urge (Muisse, 2024). Essentially, competency theory offers a framework for comprehending, evaluating, and cultivating the abilities and conduct required for successful performance in many settings. This idea is used in a number of situations, such as organizational development and education. It draws attention to the connection between these competencies and successful outcomes, whether in a work role, a school environment, or other achievement scenarios (Alharbi, 2024). Competency theory states that it's important to identify and assess certain, observable behaviours that indicate competence (Rahimi, 2024). Because competencies are often articulated in relation to specific activities, duties, or circumstances, they are pertinent and actionable (MacKinnon, 2024). Competency development is commonly seen as a process where individuals progress from unconscious incompetence to unconscious competence, in accordance with the Four Stages of Competence Model (Sposato, 2025). There are functional competencies, which are exclusive to a given job role, and core competencies, which are general and organizational. This means creating a framework that outlines the specific abilities required to be successful in a certain role or business (Chowdhury, 2024). The psychological need to grow and prove one's abilities is the main focus of this idea, along with ways to encourage this urge. Essentially, competency theory offers a framework for comprehending, evaluating, and cultivating the abilities and conduct required for successful performance in many settings.

Fig 2: Iceberg Model of Competencies of Mc Clelland 1998

Research Methodology

Research Design: The research design is quantitative. research design to find out the skills prioritize by recruiters. It's a repeated measures design as speaking and writing both the skills are rated by each HR professional. Which is specificity of paired sample test (Lin, 2024).A statistical method in the paired sample t-test, also known as the dependent sample t-test. It specifically checks to see if there is a zero-mean difference between two sets of observations. Each subject or entity should be measured twice for a paired sample t-test, producing pairs of observations. The paired sample t-test is frequently used in repeated-measures designs.

Sampling Technique: The target population was recruiters, HR Managers and Hiring professionals, who are part of recruitment team. The 19 companies from all over the Karachi were taken, out of each company, one HR professional from recruitment team was taken as sample. The total of 19 companies' data was collected. A convenient sampling technique was utilized. Sample was approached via professional networks and online platforms. Hiring professionals from diverse industries, like Information Technology, Manufacturing Industry, Educational Institutes and Health Sectors, participated in the study.

Data Collection Instrument: The data was collected through self administered Likert scale questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed through google survey form. The tool consisted of four sections. The first section is about demographic details of the participant which included their industry name, years

of experience, designation, company size etc. The second section covered perceived rating of importance of speaking skills, third section digs into perceived ratings of specific writing skills just as email writing, presentations and report writings etc. The tool consisted of 19 items and four sections. The tool was piloted to check the validity of the tool where as reliability of the tool is tested by measuring Cronbach Alpha.

Ethical Consideration: Before collecting data, the purpose of research was explained. It was clearly explained that data is being collected solely for research purpose and at any point of time participants' true identity will not be disclosed. The participants were given right to withdraw study at any point of research. The participation was voluntary. It was clarified that participants anonymity and confidentiality will be taken care of, all the data is kept in password protected files. Research data was collected with integrity and honesty. The written consent is taken via google survey form before the start of questionnaire. To guarantee the safety and welfare of the participants, ethical guidelines were meticulously followed during the whole study. All the followed guidelines were aligned with BERA framework.

Data Analysis: The data was analysed using IBM SPSS version 21.A significance level alpha of 0.05 was used for hypothesis tests. First of all, reliability of the questionnaire is measured using Cronbach Alpha, which was .813. Alpha .813 shows good internal consistency then descriptive tests were run to make

the sense of data and to overview the perceived importance ratings for speaking and writing skills. Mean median mode and standard deviation were checked in descriptives. After descriptives, the appropriateness of parametric and non parametric test was employed for subsequent analysis. Shapiro wilk test was conducted for importance ratings of communication and writing skills. The average score was calculated for specific speaking skills items and writing skills items. It was followed by the difference determination of perceived importance ratings of overall communication and perceived importance of writing skills. After the assessment of Shapiro Wilk test, a paired sample T- test was performed to compare means of both the skills.

Results:

The table 1 shows the descriptive analysis of all the items. According to the descriptives generally all the major and sub skills of writing and speaking both are rated between important and extremely important which means they are rated mostly above 4.00 on a 5-

point scale. The top-rated skill is "Ability to write professional and grammatically correct emails with 4.47 mean. It also shows that recruiters do not take written English test specifically. Written test is rarely conducted. Active listening is at 4.37 scale which shows that active listening is an indispensable area. Recruiters think English competency of fresh graduates doesn't match company's expectations; it is rated at 2.61 which is between the scale of 1 to 3 which means that the recruiters marked it between 'do not meet the expectations' of the company to rarely meet the expectations". Clear pronunciation is rated as 4.11 giving the glimpses into importance of pronunciation for career growth. Recruiters give importance to good pronunciation and enunciation. Confidence level of speaking English is demanded by recruiters by giving the rating of 4.11. Overall confidence gets 4.11 with in the range of 2-5. It shows that most of the recruiters think it highest importance on the scale of 5. Ability to use professional tone and vocabulary is demanded.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Job level in HR?	19	1	7	3.95	1.957
Industry type.	19	1	8	5.95	1.471
Employees rate in company.	19	2	4	2.89	.809
Experience in recruitment.	19	1	4	3.37	1.012
5.Ability to participate effectively in meetings and group discussions.	19	2	5	4.16	.958
6.Ability to give clear and confident presentations or public speeches.	19	2	5	4.05	.848
7.Ability to communicate clearly and persuasively.	19	1	5	4.47	.964
8.Ability to engage in professional and courteous conversation with colleagues and clients.	19	3	5	4.00	.667
9.Clear pronunciation and accent.	19	3	5	4.11	.737
10.Ability to write professional and grammatically correct emails.	19	3	5	4.47	.612
11.Ability to write clear and concise business reports or proposals.	19	2	5	4.21	.855
12.Ability to prepare written content for presentations	19	3	5	4.26	.653
13.Ability to use appropriate tone and register	19	2	5	4.05	.911
14.Active listening skills.	19	3	5	4.37	.597
15.Adaptability of communication style to different audiences .	19	3	5	4.32	.671
16.Overall confidence in using English for professional communication.	19	2	5	4.11	.809
17.Formal assessment of English communication skills as part of the hiring process for entry-level positions?	18	1	3	2.50	.618
18.English communication skills of fresh university graduates according to HR	18	1	3	2.61	.608
Valid N (listwise)	18				

Table 1.1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Speaking Skill Importance	19	13.00	25.00	20.7895	3.01070
Writing Skills Importance	19	12.00	20.00	17.0000	2.64575
Valid N (listwise)	19				

The descriptive statistics for the recruiters' assessments of the perceived importance of speaking and writing abilities are shown in Table 1. This portion of the study involved 19 companies in all. With a mean rating of 20.79 (SD=3.01), the perceived importance of speaking ability varied from a minimum score of 13.00 to a maximum score of 25.00. The perceived importance ratings for writing ability ranged from 12.00 to 20.00, with a mean of 17.00 (SD=2.65). These descriptive statistics point to

a possible discrepancy in the weight that recruiters give to these two competencies. Speaking ability importance (M=20.79) seems to be valued higher on average than writing ability important (M=17.00). The standard deviations show that among the recruiters in this sample, speaking competence ratings varied somewhat more than writing skill ratings. If this observed difference in means is statistically significant, more inferential analysis is needed, such as a paired-samples t-test.

Table 2: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Speaking Skill Importance Writing Skills Importance	3.78947	2.25041	.51628	2.70481	4.87413	7.340	18	.000

The table 2 shows the results of paired sample T -test. Since p value is .000 which is $P < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected. The mean difference of two skills is 3.7894 with standard deviation of 2,25. The t statistics are 7.340 with df 18. The 95% internal confidence difference ranges between 2.70481 and 4.874. The p value is less than 0.001. Based on the p value results the null hypothesis is rejected. Results revealed that both writing and speaking skills are important from recruiters' perspective and they give importance to both the skills yet speaking skill is a little more recommended. The results indicate that speaking skills are more important than writing skills to earn job from the recruiter's perspective which is evident from the table reading as Confidence interval of 95% with positive mean difference 3.7894.

Discussion:

The purpose of this study is to investigate how English language competency affects job prospects in the global industrial sector. The results of the study align with previous literature. English is currently a widely utilized international language as a result of significant changes brought about by globalization in business operations not just in casual conversations but also in commercial exchanges, discussions, and strategic choices (Rao, 2019; Rahmani, 2025). In tandem with this evolution, proficiency in English has emerged as a key prerequisite for employment in numerous multinational corporations, particularly those that operate across borders. Thus, a person's ability to adjust and function well in a multinational workplace is said to be indicated by their level of English proficiency as determined by their speaking and writing proficiency (Khoiruman, 2025; Roshid M. M., 2025). In addition to being the primary language of

instruction in daily life, English is now the primary means of communication in the global industrial sector, including in multinational corporations with offices or branches across multiple nations (Abro, 2025). English is used for many different things, from preparing reports, negotiating, holding business meetings, and communicating with clients and coworkers overseas (Sun, 2025). Therefore, proficiency in English is one of the skills that businesses, particularly those that operate in global markets, greatly value. English is used in internal and external communications by over 80% of international corporations, making it a crucial language for success in the global marketplace (Erimife, 2025). The findings of the study revealed multifaceted aspects of English language proficiency from the perspective of hiring personnel which aligns with previous studies.

It is found that recruiters give importance to speaking skills of new graduates at the time of hiring. A number of studies also confirm its importance. HR professionals give leverage to the candidates who are fluent in speaking and speak confidently in professional meetings and presentations (Balakrishnan, 2025). Persuasive conversation is highly recommended. Recruiters give extra point to the candidate with better pronunciation during interview (Spence, 2024). Since excellent communication is frequently a crucial component of employability, speaking abilities have a big impact on recruiters' hiring decisions for recent graduates (Lu, 2024; Molla, 2024). According to research, during interviews, recruiters value critical thinking, efficient communication, and projecting a professional image in addition to linguistic correctness. Employers look for graduates with outstanding oral communication skills, such as fluency, content appropriateness, and poise in social situations (Dülger, 2025; Roshid M. M., 2025). There is a need for improvement in these areas as many employers indicate dissatisfaction with graduates' communication abilities, especially in word usage and self-expression. Candidates are evaluated by recruiters using verbal, articulative, and nonverbal communication; verbal fluency and content relevancy are of utmost importance (Balcioglu, 2024; Sabir A. Z., 2025). The opinions of interviewers are positively impacted by successful candidates' propensity to make more consistent attributions about prior experiences.

To better prepare students for the workforce, universities are urged to improve communication training through both in-class education and hands-on experiences.

The study shows that writing skill is also important for employability. The specific writing areas which are focused by recruiters are grammar, professional vocabulary, email writing, professional report writings. Recruiters note some very unique aspects of writing like tone and register (Ho, 2021). Corporate communications have the opportunity to optimize the information architecture and communication method in addition to the program-specific CSR content. It is the fact that aspiring executives actively look for CSR material when hiring and use corporate and brand communications. Employers stated that self-expression and word use were among the areas in which oral and written communication skills needed to be improved (Johari, 2021; Aly, 2025). The abilities of recent college graduates are frequently insufficient to carry out the duties needed on the job (Singun, 2025). According to employers, students require more instruction on professional email usage, improved writing abilities, and more instruction on self-expression, impression management, and slang avoidance (Daoud, 2025; Sujinpram, 2024). In the current employment market, a candidate's prospects of getting employed are greatly impacted by their ability to compose successful emails. Strong writing abilities are becoming more and more valued by businesses since email communication has taken over as the primary means of professional communications. Numerous studies showing the discrepancy between fresh graduates' writing skills and corporate requirements support this tendency. Because email has mostly supplanted traditional communication techniques, job applicants must be proficient in this medium.

Effective speaking abilities have a substantial impact on the results of job interviews and prospects for career advancement (Ahamed, 2025). English proficiency is becoming more prized in a variety of job markets since it makes it easier to collaborate and communicate effectively in international corporate settings (Tan, 2024). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that non-linguistic factors like prosody and vocal tone can predict interview success, with particular speaking philosophies being associated with

favourable results (Määttä, 2024; Sun Y. &, 2024). Furthermore, as public speaking abilities allow people to engage and persuade others, they are crucial for leadership jobs and can influence career paths (Maharani, 2024). Being able to communicate in English is essential for employment, particularly in multicultural settings. Candidates with strong English communication skills are given preference by employers, increasing their chances of success (Datu, 2025; Fitria, 2024; Wuidar, 2025).

The results of the study align increasingly with previous national and international studies which can be seen in previous paragraphs of discussion. The overall discussion emphasizes that effective speaking abilities have a substantial impact on the results of job interviews and prospects for career advancement. English proficiency is becoming recognized in a variety of employment markets since it makes it easier to collaborate and communicate effectively in international business settings. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that non-linguistic factors like prosody and vocal tone can predict interview success, with particular speaking philosophies being associated with favourable results. Additionally, public speaking abilities are crucial for leadership positions since they allow people to influence and engage others, which in turn affects career paths.

Conclusion:

The purpose of the research is to find the importance of English language competency for job market. Young graduates strive hard to get their degrees with justified scores still they stuck in the process of getting plum jobs. This research is one step to find out recruiters' perspective and their demands from the employers. It is noticed from the data that recruiters give leverage to English language competency overall. The applicant having better confidence level in English speaking are given edge. It is found that recruiters give more edge to pronunciation along with confidence. The enunciation, overall confidence, pronunciation makes a difference in getting job. It is also clearly noticed from the paired sample t test that hiring team gives more importance to speaking skill over writing skill. Language command is achieved by working on four skills which are reading, writing, listening and speaking. It is very important to know the recruiter's perspective to give due importance to

the relevant skills required by job market. Although The study highlights that recruiters give extra edge to speaking skill over the writing skill, it is also confirmed that writing skill importance can't be neglected at the same time as the data revealed the importance of writing skill for email writing and regular job correspondence. This study also give glimpses into hiring process where writing part is totally neglected although the recruiters clearly reveal the crucial need of writing skill expertise for regular official correspondence. The study shows that command over speaking skill helps graduates to land plum jobs. Educational institutions need to emphasis on pronunciation, intonation, enunciation and professional communication aspects to hone speaking skills of fresh graduates.

Recommendations:

- Enhance the systematic integration and deliberate emphasis of speaking skill development across university curricula and co-curricular programs.
- Universities, in collaboration with career services departments and industry experts, should provide structured guidance and resources to students, empowering them to actively identify, develop, and refine high-demand career-ready skills beyond their core academic competencies.

Future Research: Qualitative follow -up to understand in-depth reason of why certain skills are valued. The study focusing certain industries and their specific skill demand can also be a productive input.

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